

Dyes Derived from 4:5 Diaryl Thiazoles

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In the present investigation a number of variously substituted *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes, their corresponding aza and diaza analogues have been prepared from 2-methyl and 2-methyl mercapto 4,5-diaryl thiazoles respectively to evaluate the effect of the replacement of $-\text{CH} = \text{CH}-$ by $-\text{CH} = \text{N}-$ and $-\text{N} = \text{N}-$ on absorption of these dyes. The absorption data have been discussed in the light of Forster's rule. The relative basicity of the different 4 : 5-diaryl thiazoles have been evaluated by using Brooker's Deviation factor.

Besides this, a number of azo dyes very much similar to diaza analogues mentioned above have been prepared for dyeing synthetic fibres. The sensitising properties of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes, their aza and diaza analogues have also been evaluated.

The present work describes the preparation of some *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes, their aza and diaza analogues derived from 2-methyl and 2-methyl-mercapto 4,5-diaryl thiazoles. Their absorption spectra have been studied and utilised in the evaluation of the effect of the replacement of $-\text{CH} = \text{CH}-$ by $-\text{CH} = \text{N}-$ and $-\text{N} = \text{N}-$ respectively in the chromophoric chain on the absorption of these dyes.

For the preparation of the *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes, their aza and diaza analogues, quaternary salts of 2-methyl and 2-methyl mercapto 4,5-diaryl thiazoles were used. The quaternary 2-methyl thiazolium iodides were prepared by heating 2-methyl 4,5-diaryl thiazoles with methyl iodide in a sealed tube. The quaternary salts of 2-methyl mercapto 4,5-diphenyl thiazoles were prepared by heating the thiazoles with methyl *p*-toluene sulphonate at 140° in an oil bath for 6 hr.

The dialkylamino styryl dyes were prepared by condensing the 2-methyl 4,5-diaryl thiazolium iodides with *p*-dimethylamino benzaldehyde in absolute alcohol in presence of piperidine. The aza analogues were prepared by treating the quaternary salts with *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline in absolute alcohol in piperidine.

For preparing the diaza analogues, the quaternary salts of 2-methylmercapto 4,5-diaryl thiazolium *p*-toluene sulphonate were condensed with 60% hydrazine hydrate giving the corresponding hydrazones.¹ The hydrazones were then condensed with (i) dimethyl aniline, (ii) diethyl aniline, (iii) N : N-dimethyl alpha-naphthylamine, (iv) 8-hydroxy quinoline in IV hydrochloric acid with a little amount of ferrous sulphate and 30% hydrogen peroxide to give the azo dyes.²

1. S. Hunig, *Leibigs. Ann.*, 1959, 56, 69, 84.

2. M. K. Rout, A. Nayak and K. K. Satpathy, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 799.

The styryl dyes ($Y = CH$, $X = CH$) their aza analogues ($Y = CH$, $X = N$) and the diaza analogues ($Y = N$, $X = N$) conform to the general structure I. The azodyes were also prepared by condensing the hydrazones with sodium salt of 2-naphthol 1-sulphonic acid in methanolic solution in presence of potassium ferricyanide and sodium carbonate at 8°. The mechanism of the condensation has been reported.²

The azo dyes were prepared with a view to study the dyeing properties of these dyes for cotton fibres. It is known that certain azodyes like II are suitable for dyeing of cellulose fabrics.

Further, these dyes are also used for the dyeing of polyester fabrics. One such dye is Astrazone red. In view of this it was considered worthwhile to study the dyeing properties specially with regard to synthetic fibres of the azo dyes prepared by us. The dyeing property is being tested at Ciba Research Centre.

The absorption maxima of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes, their corresponding aza and diaza analogues are given in Table I. The effect of replacement of $-CH = CH-$ by $-CH = N-$ and $-N = N-$ in the chromophoric chain in *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes gives rise to bathochromic shift. This experimental observation is in accordance with Forster's rule.²⁻⁶

TABLE I

Absorption maxima data of p-dialkylamino styryl dyes (I, Y = CH; X = CH), their aza (I, Y = CH, X = N) and the diaza (Y = N, X = N) analogues derived from 4:5-diaryl thiazoles

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	λmax in mμ				
		$-CH=CH-$ (a)	$-CH=N-$ (b)	Shift observed from 'a' to 'b', all bathochromic	$-N=N-$	Shift observed from 'b' to 'c', all bathochromic
H	H	498	530	32	580	50
4-Cl	H	498	550	52	605	55
H	4-Cl	520	545	25	608	63
4-OMe	H	520	546	26	614	68
H	4-OMe	515	531	16	614	83
4-Me	H	510	530	20	617	87
4-Br	H	504	535	31	605	70
H	2-Cl	493	519	26	—	—
4-F	H	510	537	27	—	—
4-C ₂ H ₅	H	499	528	29	—	—
2:5-dimethyl	H	514	533	19	—	—
H	2:4-dichloro	487	541	54	—	—

3. F. ~~W. K. Rout~~, *Z. Elektro chem.*, 1939, **45**, 548.

4. M. K. Rout, B. K. Sabata and P. C. Rath, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 803.

5. M. K. Rout, B. K. Sabata and P. C. Rath, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 78.

6. M. K. Rout, P. K. Mishra, P. K. Jesthi and P. C. Rath, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 24.

TABLE II

Deviations of p-dialkylamino styryl dyes (I) Y = CH, X = CH derived from 4 : 5-diaryl thiazoles

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	Symmetrical trimethin cyanine derived from A	λ _{max} in mμ			
			Michler's hydrol blue	Calcd.	Obs.	Deviation
H	H	589	606	595.5	498	97.5
H	4-OMe	593	606	599.5	515	84.5
4-OMe	H	597	606	601.5	520	81.5
H	4-Nitro	602	606	604.0	570	34.0
H	2-chloro	576	606	591	493	98
H	2 : 4-dichloro	576	606	591	487	104
4-Fluoro	H	590	606	598	510	88
4-Ethyl	H	590	606	598	499	99
2 : 5-dimethyl	H	593	606	599.5	514	85.5

The relative basicities of the 4,5-diaryl thiazoles employed in the preparation of the styryl dyes have been evaluated by the application of deviation factor and they conform to the following increasing order :

The same order of basicity has also been observed by Rout *et al.*² from the deviation calculation of unsymmetrically trimethin cyanines derived from alpha- and beta-naphthothiazoles and dibenzoxanthone.

The sensitisation spectra of some of these dyes have also been determined by the method already reported. To record the sensitisation spectra Agfa, BN₁ paper (sensitive range 400 to 550 mμ) was used. The following generalisations are made from the sensitisation data of these dyes.

- The *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes possess sensitising action in the regions higher than their absorption maxima.
- The dye loses its sensitising action by replacement of -CH = CH- by -CH = N- and by -N = N-.

4,5-diaryl 2-mercapto thiazoles were prepared by condensing the appropriate desyl bromides with ammonium dithiocarbamate. The analytical data are given in Table IV. The mercaptothiazoles thus obtained were methylated with dimethyl sulphate in alkaline medium to give 2-methyl mercapto compounds. They were then quaternised by heating with methyl *p*-toluene sulphonate.⁷

N-Methyl 4,5-diphenyl thiazolone hydrazone: 2-Methylmercapto 4,5-diphenyl thiazolium *p*-toluene sulphonate (1 mole; 6 g.) was then treated with hydrazine hydrate (14.2 moles, 14 g.) at 80° for one hour. The mixture was poured into water and the hydrazone filtered, washed with water and dried, m.p. 153–56°, Yield—92%. (Found: S, 11.32%; N, 14.80%; C₁₆H₁₅N₃S requires S, 11.39; N, 14.95%). The analytical data of the hydrazones thus prepared are furnished in Table V.

TABLE V

Analytical data, m.p. of *N*-methyl 4,5-diaryl thiazolone hydrazones

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	M.P °C	Yield %	% of nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.
H	H	153–56	92	14.80	14.95
4-chloro	H	53–55	87	13.26	13.31
H	4-chloro	75–80	84	13.20	13.31
4-methoxy	4-chloro	99	91	13.33	13.31
H	4-methoxy	85–87	86	13.36	13.50
4-methyl	H	74	88	14.10	14.23
H	4-methyl	113–14	83	14.21	14.23
4-Bromo	H	60–62	84	11.61	11.66

p-Dialkylamino styryl dyes and their corresponding aza analogues were prepared by the method of Rout *et al.*⁶ The analytical data of these dyes are given in Tables VI and VII respectively.

Diaza-analogues of p-dialkylamino styryl dyes: *N*-methyl 4,5-diphenyl thiazolone hydrazone (1 mole; 2.81 g.) and dimethyl aniline (1 mole; 2.1 g.) were dissolved in 80 ml. of 1N hydrochloric acid and 35 mg. of ferrous sulphate were added. Hydrogen peroxide (30%, 2.2 moles, 7.48 g.) was then added at 30°, when the dye was immediately formed.

TABLE VI

Analytical data and m.p. of styryl dyes

(I, Y = CH, X = CH)

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of C		% of H	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
H	2-chloro	65	220	55.52	55.62	4.22	4.28
4-methyl	H	74	53	60.17	60.22	4.98	5.02
4-methoxy	H	74	68	58.06	58.48	4.73	4.87
H	4-methoxy	47	55	58.26	58.48	4.78	4.87
4-Fluoro	H	81	175	57.32	57.46	4.38	4.42
4-Ethyl	H	85	220	60.24	69.76	5.13	5.24
2,5-dimethyl	H	90	125	60.31	60.76	5.02	5.24
4-Bromo	H	67	66	61.68	61.74	3.95	3.98

TABLE VII

Analytical data and m.p. of aza analogues

(I, Y = CH, Z = N)

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	Yield %	M.P. °C	% C		% H	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
H	2-chloro	70	220	53.49	53.64	3.99	4.12
H	2,4-dichloro	75	170	52.14	52.45	3.73	3.87
4-methyl	H	51	106	59.69	59.99	4.89	5.00
4-methoxy	H	44	231	58.01	58.27	4.74	4.86
H	4-methoxy	44	231	57.92	58.27	4.81	4.86
4-Fluoro	H	85	211	57.05	57.36	4.39	4.41
4-Ethyl	H	80	219	58.58	58.84	5.12	5.24
4-Bromo	H	61	115	51.39	51.57	3.92	3.97

After thirty minutes formic acid (20.0 g.) was added. The reaction mixture was heated to 70–80° on a water bath and the solution was filtered after 5 min. A saturated solution of 5 g. of sodium iodide were then added to the filtrate. The dye separated out as an iodide on cooling. It was filtered, washed with a little cold sodium iodide solution and then dried over silica gel, m.p. 72°, Yield—64% (Found : C, 54.61%; H, 4.35%; C₂₄H₂₃N₄SI requires C, 54.75%; H, 4.37%). The data relating to azo dyes prepared from the 4,5-diaryl N-methyl thiazole hydrazones and (i) dimethyl aniline, (ii) diethyl aniline, (iii) N : N-dimethyl alpha-naphthylamine and (iv) 8-hydroxy quinoline are described in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Analytical data of the azo-dyes derived from the hydrazones of 2-methyl mercapto thiazoles

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	M.P. °C	%	λ _{max}	R ₃ = <i>p</i> -dimethylamino phenyl			
					Yield	mμ	% C	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
H	H	72	64	605	54.71	54.75	4.35	4.37
4-chloro	H	78	60	614	51.30	51.39	3.90	3.92
H	4-chloro	92	61	608	51.31	51.39	3.86	3.92
4-bromo	H	84	68	610	47.56	47.60	3.62	3.64
4-methoxy	H	83	71	614	52.50	52.54	4.35	4.38
H	4-methoxy	71	63	614	52.48	52.54	4.33	4.38
4-methyl	H	86	65	617	56.55	56.59	4.69	4.72
H	4-methyl	74	62	605	56.53	56.59	4.68	4.72
R ₃ = 4-diethylamino phenyl								
H	H	84—86	65	605	56.20	56.32	4.84	4.87
4-chloro	H	63	62	620	52.98	53.02	4.40	4.42
H	4-chloro	68	64	624	52.94	53.02	4.36	4.42
4-Bromo	H	93	66	610	49.26	49.29	4.10	4.42
4-methoxy	H	64—65	63	627	55.63	55.67	4.93	4.97
H	4-methoxy	68—69	58	615	55.60	55.67	4.91	4.97
4-methyl	H	81—83	62	623	57.00	57.05	4.98	5.11
H	4-methyl	126	62	622	56.85	57.05	4.99	5.11
R ₃ = 5(8 hydroxy) quinolyl								
H	H	86	68	637	59.30	59.33	4.33	4.34
4-chloro	H	64	61	625	55.00	55.03	3.91	3.93
H	4-chloro	66	60	603	54.98	55.03	3.90	3.93
4-Bromo	H	101	68	616	51.29	51.30	3.63	3.66
4-methoxy	H	98	63	623	57.91	57.94	4.46	4.49
H	4-methoxy	96	61	625	59.60	57.94	4.45	4.49
4-methyl	H	88	64	620	58.96	58.98	4.56	4.58
H	4-methyl	189	60	625	58.91	58.93	4.53	4.58
R ₃ = 4-diethylamino naphthyl								
H	H	86	68	637	59.33	59.30	4.34	4.33
4-chloro	H	64	61	625	55.03	55.00	3.93	3.91
H	4-chloro	66	60	605	55.03	54.98	3.93	3.90
4-Bromo	H	101	68	616	51.30	51.29	3.66	3.63
4-methoxy	H	98	63	623	57.93	57.91	4.49	4.45
H	4-methoxy	96	61	625	57.94	57.91	4.49	4.46
4-methyl	H	88	64	620	58.98	58.96	4.58	4.56
H	4-methyl	189	60	625	58.98	58.91	4.58	4.53

Preparation of "Red dye" by using sodium salt of 2-naphthol 1-sulphonic acid: A solution containing 4,5-diphenyl N-methyl thiazole hydrazone (1 mole; 2.81 g.) and the sodium salt of 2-naphthol 1-sulphonic acid (1.2 moles, 2.75 g.) in 4 ml. methanol and 3.0 ml. water was stirred at 8 to 10°. Potassium ferricyanide (3.6 g.) and sodium carbonate (0.26 g.) were then added. A red dye started forming immediately and was complete in about 15 min., the mixture was then diluted with 3.0 ml. of water and the dye filtered. The dye was washed with water, filtered, and was dried over silica gel in vacuum and then crystallised from chlorobenzene, m.p. 165–68°; Yield—58.5%. (Found : C, 73.98%; H, 4.35%; C₂₅H₁₉N₃SO requires C, 74.11%; H, 4.51). The analytical data and m.p. of other compounds are given in Table IX.

TABLE IX

Analytical and absorption data of "Red dyes".

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ _{max} mμ	% C		% H	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	calcd.
H	H	165–68	58.5	526	59.62	59.9	3.58	3.65
4-chloro	H	213–15	53.5	530	59.84	56.16	3.11	3.24
H	4-chloro	97–98	62.0	526	55.91	56.16	3.01	3.24
4-Bromo	H	80–82	65.5	516	51.34	52.0	2.89	3.00
4-methoxy	H	92	58.0	536	58.59	58.8	3.68	3.81
H	4-methoxy	218–20	55.0	530	58.67	58.8	3.71	3.81
4-methyl	H	198	61.0	525	60.41	60.54	3.82	3.93
H	4-methyl	188	58.0	516	60.38	60.54	3.85	3.93

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